

1 **Title Page**

2 Investigating social orienting in children with Phelan-McDermid syndrome and ‘idiopathic’
3 autism

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33 **Abstract**

34 *Background:* Phelan-McDermid syndrome (PMS) is a rare genetic syndrome characterized by
35 developmental delay/intellectual disability, absent or delayed speech, physical dysmorphic
36 features and high rates of autistic features. However, it is currently unknown whether people
37 with PMS have similar neurocognitive atypicalities to those previously identified in idiopathic
38 autism. Disruption in social orienting has previously been suggested as an early hallmark feature
39 of idiopathic autism that impacts social learning and social interaction.

40 *Methods:* This study used a semi-naturalistic task to explore orienting to social versus non-social
41 stimuli and its relation to clinical features in individuals diagnosed with PMS, autism, and
42 neurotypical children recruited in the United States and the United Kingdom.

43 *Results:* At the group level, autistic and neurotypical children responded on average more often
44 to social than non-social stimuli, while children with PMS responded similarly to both stimulus
45 types. Both clinical groups responded significantly less often to social stimuli than neurotypical
46 children. In addition, we found considerable variability in orienting responses within each group
47 that were of clinical relevance. In the autism group, non-social orienting was associated with
48 mental age, while in the PMS group social and non-social orienting were related to strength of
49 autistic features.

50 *Conclusions:* These findings do not support specific social motivation difficulties in either
51 clinical group. However, they highlight the importance of exploring individual differences in
52 orienting responses in Phelan McDermid Syndrome in relation to clinical and functional
53 domains.

54 *Trial registration:* NA

55
56 **Keywords:** PMS; Phelan-McDermid syndrome; idiopathic autism; auditory social orienting.

57

Background

58 Phelan-McDermid syndrome (PMS), also known as 22q13.3 deletion syndrome, is a rare
59 neurodevelopmental condition caused by sequence variant in the *SHANK3* gene or deletion on
60 the long arm of terminal chromosome 22 (OMIM 606230; Phelan & McDermid, (1); Phelan,
61 (2)). PMS is characterized by a heterogeneous array of clinical features, including hypotonia,
62 absent or delayed speech, and in the vast majority (96%) of individuals intellectual disability (2,
63 3). Furthermore, approximately 65% of individuals with PMS are diagnosed with autism
64 spectrum disorder (henceforth “autism”¹) (4). Yet, the neurocognitive profile of PMS is not well
65 understood and the extent to which individuals with PMS have similar characteristics to
66 “idiopathic” autistic individuals (i-autism) remains unknown. Although the clinical profile in
67 PMS may be expected to be more homogeneous than that of i-autism, reports attest to a
68 considerable amount of clinical heterogeneity (4-6).

69 Atypical attention patterns are consistently found in autism (7, 8), with some theories
70 emphasizing either broad attention differences or differential attention to specifically social
71 information (9, 10). The social motivation hypothesis of autism proposes that reduced
72 spontaneous attention to social information is a primary feature that affects the development of
73 social cognition and social skills (e.g., (10-12). Diminished *spontaneous* orienting to social
74 stimuli (e.g., a smile), but not non-social stimuli (e.g., objects), is thought to be one of the
75 earliest manifestations of reduced social motivation. Eye-tracking studies in infants with
76 increased familial likelihood for autism have demonstrated decreased spontaneous attention to
77 social information during the viewing of static images and dynamic social scenes (13, 14).
78 Failure to respond to one’s own name being called is also identified as among one of the earliest
79 signs of autism (15, 16). A behavioral paradigm involving the presentation of social (e.g.,

¹ Henceforth referred to as autism in accordance with the preferred language of the autistic community.

80 clapping, humming) and non-social (e.g., telephone, car horn) sounds revealed that autistic
81 preschool-age children showed on average diminished orienting to social sounds, relative to both
82 typically developing children and children with developmental delay of comparable mental age
83 (17). Taken together, these data support the notion of an early social attention difficulty in
84 autism.

85 Social attention difficulties have also been linked to social-communication features in
86 several studies (18-21). For example, Murias et al. (18) found that in autistic toddlers, less
87 attention to social bids was associated with lower scores on several measures of
88 socio-communicative behavior. Relatedly, autistic toddlers who looked less often at social scenes
89 showed more autistic core features (19). Studies with autistic adolescents and adults indicate that
90 this relationship between social attention and social-communication features persists through to
91 adulthood (11, 22, 23).

92 A separate hypothesis proposes that autism may involve more global, domain-general
93 attentional differences, resulting in difficulties orienting and shifting of attention regardless of
94 stimulus type (24, 25). Supporting this idea, one study found that autistic children had difficulty
95 with attention disengagement as compared to typically developing controls, regardless of the
96 social nature of the stimuli (26). Sasson et al. (27) also found that across non-social and social
97 arrays, autistic children showed domain-general difficulties in disengagement. There is also
98 evidence that atypical neurobiological development of attention networks in autism contributes
99 to global impairments in attention (28). Given the considerable clinical and etiological
100 heterogeneity in autism, it is plausible that some individuals have domain-general attentional
101 difficulties, others attend less to specifically social information, and that attention patterns vary
102 between individuals.

103 In contrast to the relatively robust literature on social and non-social attention in autism,
104 there has been little research examining attentional patterns in individuals with PMS. To address

105 this gap in knowledge, the present study pooled data from two clinical natural history studies of
106 individuals with PMS carried out simultaneously in the United States (US) and the United
107 Kingdom (UK). Both sites employed an established social orienting paradigm (17) to investigate
108 whether individuals with PMS show less orienting to specifically social stimuli or present with
109 general difficulties in attention orienting. Our aims were to examine: 1) average group
110 differences between the PMS, i-autism and neurotypical groups in orienting patterns, and 2) the
111 relationships between individual differences in orienting responses and measures of
112 social-communicative features, cognitive and social adaptive functioning.

113 The social motivation hypothesis predicts that individual with PMS, like autistic children,
114 would orient specifically less to social but not non-social stimuli, and that the frequency of social
115 orienting would be negatively related to autistic features and positively related to social adaptive
116 functioning skills in both groups. Alternatively, if PMS-related attention difficulties were more
117 linked to their overall intellectual level, we would expect to find equal impairments for both
118 social and non-social orienting, with these generalized impairments relating to intellectual
119 functioning. Studying these differences will bring us closer to understanding the cognitive profile
120 of PMS individuals, to ultimately provide them with better and more tailored care.

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Methods

Participants

125 The study was conducted simultaneously at two separate sites: the Seaver Center for Research
126 and Treatment at Mount Sinai (New York) in the US, and the Institute of Psychiatry, Psychology
127 and Neuroscience (London) in the UK. Approval was obtained by the respective ethics
128 committee at each site. Children and young adults with PMS were recruited through the PMS
129 family foundations in the US or in the UK. Additionally, two British families were recruited via

130 referral from genetic clinics in the local area. In total, the study included 67 participants with
131 PMS: 46 from the US and 21 from the UK. PMS diagnosis was confirmed through molecular
132 genetic testing. Fifty-four autistic participants also participated: 23 from the research
133 center in the US, and 31 from special needs schools in the wider London area (UK). All autistic
134 participants were previously diagnosed using the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental
135 Disorders, Fourth Edition -Revised or Fifth Editions (DMS-IV-TR or DSM-5; American
136 Psychological Association, (29) and (30) respectively), or the International Classification of
137 Diseases (ICD-10; World Health Organization, (31)) criteria. Participants ranged in age from 1.5
138 to 24 years of age (or 19 to 293 months). Across sites, greater numbers of males were included in
139 the i-autism groups, whereas sex was distributed evenly in the PMS group, consistent with
140 published reports. To match the delayed language and cognitive profile of the PMS group, only
141 minimally verbal (no words, single words, or one-clause sentences) and/or intellectually disabled
142 autistic individuals were enrolled (Table 1) (intellectual disability encompasses individuals with
143 $IQ \geq 70$, and/or impaired adaptive functioning and these difficulties are apparent during
144 development). For referential purposes to compare responses to a non-clinical sample, a group of
145 28 neurotypical/typically developing (TD) children were also recruited in the UK following the
146 same procedures as with the PMS and i-autism individuals. TD children ranged in age from 1.5
147 to 6 years.

148

149 *Procedure*

150 Autistic features

151 To assess autistic features, participants in the PMS and i-autism groups were administered the
152 Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule 2nd Edition (ADOS-2; (32)) and caregivers were
153 administered the Autism Diagnostic Interview – Revised (ADI-R; (33)). The Calibrated Severity
154 Score (CSS; calculated from (34) and (35)), the Total score, and the Social Affect and Repetitive

155 and Restrictive Behaviors sub-scores from the ADOS-2, as well as the
156 Language/Communication, Reciprocal Social Interactions, and Repetitive Behaviors/Interests
157 domain scores from the ADI-R were used to characterize clinical severity. Although this is not
158 confirmatory of diagnosis, across sites, 66 of 67 individuals with PMS (99%) had an ADOS-2
159 performed and 64 (97%) met criteria for autism or autism spectrum. Similarly, for the ADI-R, 66
160 of 67 PMS participants had the instrument administered and 58 (89%) met criteria for
161 abnormalities in reciprocal social interaction (domain A), 58 (89%) for abnormalities in
162 communication (domain B), and 45 (68%) for restricted, repetitive, and stereotyped patterns of
163 behavior (domain C). Eighty-three percent of individuals with PMS at the US site also met
164 criteria for autism based on consensus diagnosis using ICD or DSM criteria and informed by the
165 ADOS-2 and ADI-R. All autistic participants met clinical ICD or DSM criteria for autism.
166 Cognitive profile

167 In all groups, mental age was assessed using a range of measures depending on the
168 participant's language and ability level. For example, the Mullen Scales of Early Learning
169 (MSEL; (36)) was used for children below age five years and/or with mental age estimates below
170 the floor of other age-appropriate test options. For those above this cut off, the US site used the
171 Stanford Binet Intelligence Scales – Fifth Edition (37), the Differential Ability Scales II - Early
172 Years (38), or the Leiter International Performance Scale (39). The UK site used the Wechsler
173 Abbreviated Scales of Intelligence - 2nd Edition (40) or a combination of the Raven's Coloured
174 Progressive Matrices (41) and the British Picture Vocabulary Scale 3rd Edition (42). Verbal
175 mental age (VMA) was computed from the average of the Receptive Language and the
176 Expressive Language mental ages of the MSEL or calculated from the verbal intelligence
177 quotient (VIQ) subscales of other instruments (i.e., $VDQ = VMA/CA*100$). Similarly,
178 non-verbal mental age (NVMA) was calculated using the average of the Visual Reception and
179 Fine Motor mental ages of the MSEL or non-verbal IQ of the other measures.

180 The Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales 2nd Edition (Vineland-II; (43)) Survey Interview
181 Form was administered to parents to assess their child’s adaptive functioning in everyday life.
182 Standard scores (mean = 100, SD = 15) from three main domains (Communication,
183 Socialization, and Daily Living Skills), as well as the Adaptive Behavior Composite (ABC) were
184 used to relate social orienting variables to everyday functioning.

185 Table 1 presents the chronological and mental ages, Vineland-II, ADOS-2, and ADI-R
186 scores for each group. Despite significant differences between groups in developmental level and
187 most of the adaptive behavior domains, the i-autism and PMS groups did not significantly differ,
188 in social communication features on the ADOS-2, ADI-R, or the Vineland-II. However, in terms
189 of restrictive and repetitive behaviors, the i-autism group scored on average significantly higher
190 than the PMS group on the ADI-R.

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Table 1. Descriptors for age and sex and social variables by diagnosis (Mean (SD) [range])

	PMS	i-autism	TD	p^a	Post-hoc
<i>N</i>	67	50	28	-	-
Sex (m:f)	33:34	46:4	17:11	<.001	PMS – autism** PMS - TD ns autism - TD**
CA (months)	92.43 (51.96) [19-293]	90.77 (42.07) [34-227]	48.73 (19.71) [19-83]	<.001	PMS - autism ns PMS>TD*** autism>TD***
NVMA (months)	22.27 (21.95) [4.95-89.01]	36.67 (38.14) [1-246.03]	60.71 (37.12) [17-143]	<.001	PMS<autism*** PMS<TD*** autism<TD***
VMA (months)	23.35 (22.41) [2.0-86.94]	33.04 (22.79) [4.5-132.13]	64.60 (44.97) [11-179]	<.001	PMS<autism*** PMS<TD*** autism<TD***
Vineland Communication	50.40 (14.86) [21-91]	62.09 (19.06) [36-116]	111.21(14.54) [84-141]	<.001	PMS<autism*** PMS<TD*** autism<TD***
Vineland Daily Living	51.52 (13.91) [21-82]	61.72 (15.48) [34-97]	98.57 (12.92) [71-125]	<.001	PMS<autism** PMS<TD*** autism<TD***
Vineland Socialization	57.67 (15.10) [20-101]	60.02 (15.6) [40-108]	101.36 (11.44) [79-126]	<.001	PMS – autism ns PMS<TD*** autism<TD***
Vineland Composite	51.61 (13.11) [20-83]	60.70 (13.81) [39-92]	102.86 (13.47) [84-131]	<.001	PMS<autism** PMS<TD*** autism<TD***
ADOS CSS	7.00 (2.04) [1-10]	7.04 (1.78) [3-10]	NA	.905	NA
ADOS Total	17.39 (5.83) [2-27]	17.62 (5.37) [6-28]	NA	.962	NA
ADOS SA	14.21 (4.79) [2-20]	13.58 (4.24) [3-20]	NA	.280	NA
ADOS RRB	3.18 (2.08) [0-8]	4.04 (2.21) [0-8]	NA	.051	NA
ADI-R RecSoc	18.86 (8.98) [0-30]	20.69 (8.00) [0-30]	NA	.454	NA
ADI-R Communication	12.54 (5.54) [0-25]	14.62 (5.93) [0-23]	NA	.075	NA
ADI-R RRB	3.47 (2.37) [0-10]	6.69 (1.89) [3-10]	NA	<.001*	NA

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$a = p$ for Kruskal-Wallis or Mann-Whitney depending on the number of groups to compare; ns = non-significant; * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$; NA = not applicable; CA = Chronological Age; NVMA = Non-Verbal Mental Age; VMA = Verbal Mental Age; Vineland = Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scale, ADOS = Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule; CSS = Calibrated Severity Score; SA = Socio-Affective; RRB = Repetitive and Restrictive Behaviors; RecSoc = Reciprocal Social Interaction.

198 Social orienting task

199 To assess social attention, we used the established Dawson et al. (17) paradigm. Social orienting
200 was always completed before the ADOS-2 at the US site and afterwards at the UK site. For this
201 task, one examiner sat in front of the child while engaged in a neutral activity, such as looking at
202 a picture book. A second examiner waited until the child was engaged in the activity, and then
203 delivered each stimulus. The auditory stimuli consisted of four social (humming a neutral tone;
204 calling the child's name; snapping fingers; patting hands on thighs) and four non-social (timer
205 beep; phone ringing; whistle; car horn) sounds. Each stimulus was delivered three times per trial
206 with a one second interval in between. For each stimulus, if the child turned his/her head and/or
207 eyes toward the stimulus within 15 seconds of delivery, it was coded as successful orienting (i.e.,
208 1). If s/he did not turn his/her head and/or eyes toward the stimulus, or took longer than 15
209 seconds, non-orienting was coded (i.e., 0). The total number of orienting responses was
210 computed separately for social and non-social stimuli. Therefore, the possible scores for
211 responses to either social or non-social stimuli could range between 0 and 4, with higher scores
212 indicating better orienting responses. To explore the general orienting tendency to sounds, a total
213 composite score was also calculated by adding all social and non-social positive responses. All
214 sessions were videotaped and reviewed by a third rater to resolve any coding discrepancy
215 between examiners.

216 Of note, small differences in administration existed across sites. At the US site, all stimuli
217 were administered from around the room (behind-left, behind-right, front-left, front-right), with
218 order and location of the stimuli counterbalanced across participants ($n = 8$ total trials). At the
219 UK site, all eight sounds were presented following a pseudorandom stimuli presentation
220 sequence, from the front-left and front right, and then again from the behind-left and behind-
221 right, or vice versa in a counterbalanced fashion ($n = 16$ total trials). For the UK site, post-testing
222 analyses revealed significantly more orienting responses when stimuli were delivered from the

223 front rather than from the back for PMS and autistic individuals (all $p < .016$ - see Appendix 1a)
224 and not for TD children (all $p > .55$), but first or second position order (i.e. front then back versus
225 back then front) made no difference, indicating a lack of priming effect (all $p > .060$ – see
226 Appendix 1b). Therefore, to account for the double presentation of stimuli and to be equivalent
227 to the results from the US, the total number of orienting responses were divided by two. Three
228 UK participants were too agitated and could not be administered all the stimuli; in those cases,
229 the response to their total number of stimuli presented (if at least two bids per condition were
230 administered) was pro-rated by using the average score of the valid trials.

231

232 *Analysis*

233 All analyses were completed using IBM SPSS® version 26, and figures were created using the
234 *ggplot2* library (44) in *R*. Group comparisons between all three groups were conducted using
235 Kruskal-Wallis tests. Since responses on the orienting conditions were non-normally distributed,
236 the Wald test was used to explore condition by diagnosis effects. Mann-Whitney U tests were
237 used in all cases for post-hoc tests. To explore the weight of the independent variables of interest
238 (i.e. verbal and non-verbal mental ages, ADOS Calibrated Severity Scores and Vineland
239 Socialization sub-domain scores) these were entered into a liner regression model with social or
240 non-social orienting responses as dependent variable, divided by group.

241

242 **Results**

243 *Social orienting results*

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245 Mean-group differences were explored in relation to the number of orienting responses. Figure 1
246 shows the distribution of scores for stimulus type (i.e., social vs non-social) by group. There
247 were significant mean group differences in orienting between all three groups ($W_{(2)} = 2.61$,

248 $p < .001$), between social and non-social conditions ($W_{(1)} = 16.27, p < .001$) and in the interaction
249 between group and condition ($W_{(2)} = 5.83, p < .001$). Post-hoc analyses showed that in the social
250 condition, the i-autism and PMS groups scored significantly lower on average than TD children
251 while there were no significant group differences in the non-social condition. Within-group
252 comparisons revealed that both i-autism and TD groups responded, on average, more often to
253 social than non-social stimuli. By contrast, in the PMS group, average scores did not differ
254 between conditions.

255 However, as can also be seen from individual scores within the box plots, there was wide
256 variability in responses in all groups. Except for TD children in the social condition, scores
257 covered the whole range from 0 to 4 in each condition.

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Figure 1. Distribution of scores and comparison a) by type of stimuli between groups, and b) within groups by type of stimuli. Bars between box plots represent significant values (NS. = non-significant; * $p < .05$) for mean differences between groups. Red dots indicate the group mean.

264 To check whether a clinical diagnosis of autism could account for the heterogeneity in the
265 PMS group, we created a “proxy diagnosis” by using the scores from the ADOS and ADI-R.
266 Participants who scored above cut off for autism or autism spectrum on the ADOS and above cut
267 off in all three domains of the ADI-R were classified as having autism. We subsequently studied
268 the differences in social and non-social orienting scores for those PMS individuals classified as
269 having autism versus those who did not. We found no significant mean group differences in the
270 scores between these two groups. Similarly, given the almost even proportion of males and
271 females in the PMS, but not in the i-autism group, we studied differences between sexes in the
272 PMS group to explore whether sex could be accounting for differences in performance. Again,
273 results showed no significant mean group differences between both sexes in either task
274 condition. Given these results, we decided to keep all PMS individuals together (irrespective of
275 diagnosis or sex) to ensure a sample sufficiently large for analyses. Detailed analyses can be
276 found in Appendix 2.

277
278 Total orienting scores (combining social and non-social orienting response bids) were
279 significantly different between the PMS ($M = 4.27$, $SD = 2.26$), i-autism ($M = 4.24$, $SD = 1.76$)
280 and TD groups ($M = 4.85$, $SD = 1.77$; $K_{(2)} = 8.04$, $p = .04$), although post-hoc groups revealed no
281 mean significant differences between pairs (all $p > .19$).

282
283 *Multiple linear regressions with autism-related measures*

284 To understand the association of task performance and clinical profile, orienting scores were
285 examined in relationship to age (both chronological and mental), level of autism features (as
286 measured by the ADOS-2 CSS), and level of social adaptive functioning (as measured by the
287 Vineland-II). Regression coefficients and model fit statistics are presented in Table 2. These
288 models explained 33% and 34% of the variance in social and non-social orienting in the PMS
289 group and 39% in the i-autism group, only for non-social orienting. Mental ages combined with

290 social adaptive ability were significant for the responses to both stimuli in the TD control group.
291 While severity of autistic features predicted the number of orienting responses in both models for
292 the PMS group, in autistic individuals, verbal and non-verbal mental ages predicted most
293 variance in non-social orienting behavior.
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Table 2. Multiple linear regressions models for both types of orienting scores with verbal and non-verbal mental ages, Vineland Socialization sub-domain scores, and ADOS-2 Calibrated Severity Scores, by group.

PMS										
Social						Non-Social				
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	R^2_{adj}	<i>Model fit</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	R^2_{adj}	<i>Model fit</i>
Constant	3.613	1.001				2.640	1.026			
NVMA	-0.007	0.019	-0.124			-0.005	0.019	-0.075		
VMA	0.034	0.018	0.592			0.028	0.018	0.462		
VABS Soc	-0.011	0.011	-0.134			0.005	0.011	0.063		
ADOS CSS	-0.201	0.080	-0.315*	.327	$F_{(4,54)} = 6.569, p < .001^{***}$	-0.0206	0.082	-0.313*	.340	$F_{(4,54)} = 6.97, p < .001^{***}$

i-autism										
Social						Non-Social				
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	R^2_{adj}	<i>Model fit</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	R^2_{adj}	<i>Model fit</i>
Constant	0.866	1.082				0.672	0.996			
NVMA	-0.009	0.008	-.3608			-0.022	0.007	-0.814**		
VMA	0.025	0.013	0.559			0.054	0.012	1.143***		
VABS Soc	0.013	0.011	0.198			-0.003	0.010	-0.043		
ADOS CSS	0.007	0.098	0.012	.167	$F_{(4,32)} = 1.600, p = .198$	0.028	0.090	0.043	.394	$F_{(4,32)} = 5.214, p = .002^{**}$

TD										
Social						Non-Social				
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	R^2_{adj}	<i>Model fit</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	R^2_{adj}	<i>Model fit</i>
Constant	2.064	2.126				2.253	1.515			
NVMA	-0.013	0.036	-0.170			-0.030	0.026	-0.649		
VMA	-0.008	0.027	-0.157			0.021	0.019	0.609		
VABS Soc	0.005	0.023	0.047	-.001	$F_{(3,23)} = 1.483, p = .413$	0.010	0.016	0.131	-.064	$F_{(3,23)} = 0.480, p = .70$

NVMA = Non-Verbal Mental Age; VMA = Verbal Mental Age; VABS = Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scale; Soc = Socialization; ADOS = Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule; CSS = Calibrated Severity Score; B = coefficient B; SE = standard error; β : standardised regression coefficient; R^2_{adj} = adjusted R squared; Residuals from regression models were approximately normally distributed and collinearity diagnostics suggested no multicollinearity between variables. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .0125$ (significant after Bonferroni correction; $p = .05/4$).

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Discussion

This study compared orienting responses to social and non-social stimuli between individuals with PMS, autistic children and neurotypical children, using a well-known semi-naturalistic social orienting paradigm (17). Based on the social motivation hypothesis, we predicted that both clinical groups would react less often specifically to social but not non-social stimuli, as previously demonstrated in samples of idiopathic autistic children. We also tested the competing hypothesis that lower responses to either stimulus type may be related to intellectual disability. Findings showed that although both clinical groups responded less often to social stimuli than the neurotypical group (and didn't significantly differ from each other), within-group comparisons by stimulus type revealed that the i-autism group responded relatively more often to social than non-social stimuli. The PMS group showed a different pattern, displaying on average lower rates of social and non-social orienting, in line with more domain-general attentional difficulties. Hence, our results did not replicate previous findings (17, 45) of specific difficulties with social orienting in autistic children and they did not find this pattern in the PMS group.

There are several factors that may have contributed to the unexpected finding in the i-autism group. Autistic participants in this study were generally older and represented a broader range of ages than some previous studies of social orienting to match the age range in the PMS group. Age and verbal mental age have been shown to play an important role in the acquisition of other aspects of social cognition in autism, such as a theory of mind (46, 47). Perhaps there are true difficulties in social orienting in the early years, and that (some) autistic children learn with age, or receive training through intervention, to orient to relevant stimuli of social content, and to disregard background environmental noises (e.g., car horn, etc.) (48). Unfortunately, we did not collect information on earlier development or possible interventions, and so could not test this hypothesis. These possibilities are, however,

333 consistent with more recent studies of social attention in i-autism using eye-tracking tasks
334 that also did not find universal difficulties in attending to social stimuli (49), including in
335 older children (50).

336 In contrast, group level findings in the PMS group suggest similar difficulties in
337 responding to both social and non-social stimuli. This finding is in line with previous results
338 from a passive listening task in a small sample of children with PMS showing no differences
339 in brain responses to social vs. non-social sounds while undergoing an MRI (51). Given that
340 the PMS group was, on average, mentally younger than the autistic participants, it is possible
341 that discrimination between relevant and irrelevant stimuli has not yet been developed and
342 could account for this lack of differences. Similarly, given that all our participants presented
343 with intellectual disability, this could be the reflection of their overall developmental delay,
344 and the impact of a delayed processing speed and/or mental capacity.

345 The present findings also highlight considerable individual differences in social and
346 non-social attention in both clinical groups. Studies often focus on mean group differences
347 but neglect the rich information that individual patterns provide. This is particularly notable
348 in studies with rare genetic conditions, which often rely on small sample sizes. However,
349 with increasing recognition of heterogeneity of autism, some studies have begun to examine
350 individual differences in social attention among autistic individuals (49) and their relevance
351 to other clinical features (52). Indeed, at both our clinical sites we found ample variability of
352 orienting responses not only among the i-autistic participants but also among the participants
353 with PMS. While some individuals oriented to all stimuli regardless of their nature, others
354 oriented to almost none. Yet other individuals showed a preference for either social or
355 non-social stimuli.

356 To explore the relationship between orienting responses and clinical heterogeneity,
357 we examined the role of mental age, autistic features and social adaptive behavior in the

358 responses to social and non-social bids. This revealed differential relationships in the three
359 groups. Contrary to the hypothesis that social orienting impacts social-communication, in the
360 i-autism group, autistic features did not explain variance in the number of social orienting
361 responses. Instead, higher verbal mental age and lower non-verbal mental age predicted more
362 frequent orienting to non-social stimuli. It appears that as autistic children's verbal abilities
363 increase, so too does their ability to orient to non-social auditory stimuli, which could help
364 increasing flexibility. In the neurotypical children group, social orienting was neither related
365 to verbal or non-verbal mental age or level of social adaptive behavior. These findings also
366 indicate that within the current age/mental age brackets, social orienting behavior alone could
367 not predict clinically relevant levels of autistic features and/or adaptive behavior in autistic
368 and neurotypical children.

369 By contrast, in the PMS group responses to both types of stimuli were strongly related
370 to level of autistic features. This finding suggests that orienting behavior (regardless of
371 stimulus type) may be of clinical relevance in PMS. If this finding replicates in other samples
372 and shows good test-retest reliability, spontaneous orienting behavior may be explored as an
373 objective measure for therapeutic interventions targeting autistic features in PMS. The social
374 orienting paradigm is brief, easy to administer and score, and, unlike other measures of social
375 attention (i.e., eye-tracking), does not rely on expensive equipment or require participants to
376 sit still and attend for long periods of time. This may make social orienting a particularly
377 useful tool among this population.

378 This study had several key strengths. To date, relatively little research has studied
379 the social cognitive development of people with PMS and examined similarities or
380 differences to idiopathic autism. This is due to the fact that most paradigms are unsuitable for
381 children with severe and profound intellectual disability. The social orienting task is suitable
382 for people with severe or profound intellectual disability, and arguably more naturalistic than

383 even eye-tracking tasks (which require participants to look at a screen); therefore, results may
384 be more representative of real-life responses. Furthermore, given the rarity of PMS, it is
385 noteworthy that we have combined a relatively large sample of participants with PMS across
386 two sites to examine behavioral differences in a lab-based context. This enables us to draw
387 more robust conclusions than those based on smaller sample sizes, and to begin to investigate
388 individual differences among people with PMS.

389 Some limitations are also worth noting. First, there were slight differences in
390 administration between sites in the location pattern and amount of stimulus delivery.
391 Statistical measures were nevertheless taken to minimize the impact of such differences.
392 Another limitation is the difference in mental age between all three groups. However,
393 although the i-autism group had on average higher IQ than the PMS group, considerable
394 efforts were made to recruit autistic children with moderate to severe ID, a subgroup of
395 autistic people that is often overlooked in clinical research. Furthermore, analyses of
396 between-group differences between were not corrected for multiple comparisons forcing us to
397 interpret these results with caution. Finally, as is typical in studies with autistic individuals,
398 the male to female ratio was significantly more uneven than in the other two groups. To
399 mitigate this problem, we tested for possible orienting differences in the other clinical group
400 (i.e., PMS) and found no difference between sexes, concluding that sex, on this occasion, was
401 not a relevant variable for performance in the PMS group.

402

403

Conclusions

404 This study compared social and non-social orienting patterns between individuals
405 with PMS, idiopathic autistic children and neurotypical children using a semi-naturalistic
406 auditory orienting task. Although both clinical groups responded less often to social stimuli
407 compared to the neurotypical children, contrary to the social motivation hypothesis of autism,

408 lower orienting responses were not specific to social content. The autistic group responded
409 overall significantly more often to social than non-social stimuli while the PMS group
410 responded on average to both stimulus types at the same rate. However, we also observed
411 notable individual differences in orienting pattern in both clinical groups. This is particularly
412 significant for the PMS group as most previous studies of PMS (and rare genetic syndromes)
413 assumed greater homogeneity relative to idiopathic autism and rarely studied individual
414 variability. Future studies will need to further examine the relationship between
415 neurocognitive profile and clinical features in PMS and may explore the potential of orienting
416 behaviors as outcome measure in clinical trials.

417	List of abbreviations
418	ABC: Adaptive Behavior Composite
419	ADI-R: Autism Diagnostic Interview – Revised
420	ADOS-2: Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule 2 nd Edition
421	ASD: Autism Spectrum Disorder
422	CSS: Calibrated Severity Score
423	DMS: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders
424	i-autism: idiopathic autism
425	ICD: International Classification of Diseases
426	MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging
427	MSEL: Mullen Scales of Early Learning
428	NVIQ: Non-Verbal Intelligent Quotient
429	NVMA: Non-Verbal Mental Age
430	PMS: Phelan-McDermid syndrome
431	RRB: Repetitive and Restrictive Behaviors
432	SA: Social Affect
433	TD: Typically Developing
434	Vineland-II: Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales 2nd Edition
435	VIQ: Verbal Intelligence Quotient
436	VMA: Verbal Mental Age

437

Declarations

438 *Ethics approval and consent to participate*

439 In the UK, the project was approved by the National Research Ethics Service (NRES)
440 Committee London – Queen Square, under reference 15/LO/0305. All volunteers and their
441 families gave appropriate consent/assent to participate in the study. In the US, the project was
442 approved by the Institutional Review Board at the Mount Sinai Hospital. All participants and
443 their families gave appropriate consent to participate in the study.

444

445 *Consent for publication*

446 NA

447

448 *Availability of data and materials*

449 The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the
450 corresponding author on reasonable request.

451

452 *Competing interests*

453 AK receives research support from AMO Pharma and consults to Ovid Therapeutics, Acadia,
454 and Alkermes. ASJC has been a consultant for F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd, consults for
455 Servier and Signant Health, and she has been involved in clinical trials conducted by Servier.
456 The present work is unrelated to the above grants and relationships. All other authors have no
457 competing interests to declare (EL, JC, JFF, PS, EW, DH, AD, DVC, VB, CB, DGM, MN).

458

459 *Funding*

460 Work in the UK was supported by EU-AIMS (European Autism Interventions), which
461 receives support from the Innovative Medicines Initiative Joint Undertaking under grant
462 agreement no. 115300, the resources of which are composed of financial contributions from
463 the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (grant FP7/2007-2013), from the
464 European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations companies' in-kind
465 contributions, and from Autism Speaks. This project was also supported by the Innovative
466 Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 777394. This Joint
467 Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
468 innovation programme and EFPIA and SFARI, Autistica, and AUTISM SPEAKS. The
469 funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of
470 data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results. Any views
471 expressed are those of the author(s) and not necessarily those of the funders. Work in the US
472 was supported by the Beatrice and Samuel A. Seaver Foundation and the National Institute of
473 Mental Health (R34 MH100276; PI: Kolevzon). MN was supported by a Beatriz Galindo
474 Senior Fellowship (Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, BGP18700186) and the
475 Comunidad de Madrid (S12/PBG/2020-00016).

476

477 *Authors' Contributions*

478 AK and EL were involved in the conception of the study design and analysis and acted as
479 joint senior authors in critically revising the article. EW and ASJC cleaned, analyzed, and
480 interpreted the data and wrote the article in full. AK, JHF, EL and JC contributed to the
481 design of the analysis and drafting the article. EW, ASJC, JC, MN, CB, DH, AD, and PS
482 collected the data for this study and VB helped to collate and clean it. All authors approved
483 the final version to be published.

484

485 *Acknowledgements*

486 We thank all participants and their families for their time and effort in participating in the
487 study. We also acknowledge the contributions of the EU-AIMS and AIMS-2-TRIALS
488 consortia and in particular, the EU-AIMS SynaG team who has helped collect data at
489 different moments during the study: Jumana Ahmad, Claire Ellis, Amy Goodwin, Hannah
490 Hayward, Megan Leverington, Sarah Longstaffe, Hannah Meyer-Lindenberg, Bethany
491 Oakley, Jessica Sabet, Chiara Terzo, and Carrie Toptan. We acknowledge the contributions
492 of the research team at Seaver Autism Center, particularly Kristin Meyering and Jordana
493 Weissman.

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